

Studies on Storage Behavior of Cabbage Head as Influenced by Organic Amendments and Inorganic Fertilizers

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Abstract : The influence of organic amendments and inorganic fertilizers on cabbage head was investigated to determine their effect on storage behavior and organoleptic quality. Field cabbage was raised by combining fourteen different treatments comprising of organic amendments and inorganic fertilizers at different levels. The result showed that nutrient schedule of the crop significantly influenced the physiological loss in weight (PLW) and organoleptic quality of cabbage head and judicious selection of nutrient combination can extend the storage life and reduce the post harvest deterioration of head. The nutrient schedule comprising of higher level of FYM (16 t ha⁻¹) along with 75% of recommended inorganic fertilizers in conjugation with seedling inoculation of biofertilizer emerged as potential nutrient source for improving storage life, marketability and maintaining nutritional and organoleptic quality under ambient storage condition.

Keywords : Cabbage head, Organic amendments, Organoleptic quality, Physiological loss in weight (PLW)

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